

Business Incubator's Success Factors : Scale Development and Refinement

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Abstract : *Business incubators/incubation centres play an important role globally in developing innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem. They have evolved as highly efficient systems for the economic development of industrialized nations. This study tries to identify the measures of incubation performance and further delves into developing a research instrument comprising measures of Business incubator performance. This research instrument was refined and tests for reliability and validity were performed. The measures which are critical to the performance of business incubators are identified from the literature and it was found that the role of networking is critical and influences business incubator performance, other factors such as University linkage and incubation facilities provided to the startup firms also play an important role as far as business incubator performance is concerned. Further, research scale was refined and tested through CFA for assessing the measurement model, where scales were found unidimensional. The present study thus develops a conceptual model and a research instrument that would help managers in executing their functions by focusing on these critical areas for the enhancement of business incubator performance.*

Keywords : Business Incubators, Entrepreneurship, Startup, University Linkages, Networking.

1. Introduction

Every country tries to focus on knowledge & technology augmentation for innovation and entrepreneurship. These areas are on the priority in their development agenda as they are critical for advancement. Developing countries are always in search of new inventions which are going on around the globe

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and try to innovate indigenously that can be adapted to their local conditions. Now majority of them focus on trying to create conditions in which entrepreneurship and innovation lead to socioeconomic development. The importance of entrepreneurship in creating employment opportunities, innovative products/services and the formation of new business firms is seen as the engine of economic growth and progress (Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999; Khalil and Oiafen, 2010; Audretsch et al., 2016). Developing countries realised the potential of startups, started implementing policies to encourage entrepreneurs by offering financial and non-financial incentives through a variety of sources (Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999). These initiatives support the startup culture and assist small and medium-sized businesses in acquiring cutting-edge equipment and management techniques.

The first business incubator was formed in the United States back in the 1960s to stimulate innovation and encourage entrepreneurship (Lewis, 2003). By providing infrastructure and other support services, business incubation, a sub-discipline of entrepreneurship, aids in the development of new businesses, their early survival, sustainment, achievement of growth, and improvement of the chances of progress in nascent years (Bergek and Norman 2008; Ramussen 2011). Business incubators are viewed as an effective tool by the macro authorities and decision-makers for fostering innovation and economic growth. In emerging countries, Incubators can significantly benefit entrepreneurs by increasing human capital and developing their networking (Abdelgawad, 2022). Additionally, business incubators play an important role in the formation of new technology-based growth enterprises in these domains. The goal of a business incubator is to aid the entrepreneurial team with various tangible and intangible resources in the development of a new company (Nair and Blomquist, 2019; Mohan and Chinchwadkar, 2022). In order to achieve this, they offer their services and participate in endeavours that aid in the creation of high-tech startups with a scalable business model.

By using a business incubation mechanism, which offers specialised services like shared office space, business counselling, and knowledge sharing, new firms are nurtured and closely watched in the early stages of growth (Birch, 1979; Gissy, 1984; Allen and Rahman, 1985; Deyanova et al., 2022). It is crucial to determine the success elements for effective incubation. This study tried to develop and refine a research instrument comprising antecedents and measures of Business incubator performance.

2. Literature Review

An elaborative and orderly literature related to business incubation was keenly reviewed by various author such as Allen and Rahman (1985), Mian (1996), Hackett and Dilts (2004) and Theorakopoulos et al. (2014) in order to provide a systematic platform for entrepreneurial activities by doing a critical assessment of business incubation.

Despite the consistent definition of a business incubator, it converges three dimensions as business incubation model itself, its very purpose and the support services it provides to startups (Ayyash et al., 2020). As stated in the description of business incubators, these organisations assist entrepreneurs in combining their concepts into a cohesive whole and sustaining business by mentoring and guiding them from the starting so that the new venture can transform into a growing and a successful business enterprise (NBIA 2010).

Business incubators become an essential policy tool for promoting the growth and development of entrepreneurship and business start-ups. Through its external networks, business incubators assist tenant companies in generating entrepreneurial value (Nair and Blomquist, 2019). The objective of the business incubators is intended to improve the survival rate as well as scaling up of newly launched businesses by offering a method for identifying companies that are constrained by a lack of resources and managerial assistance (Ayatse et al., 2017; Pattanasak, 2022). It includes the provision of facilities ranging from physical infrastructure, guidance and mentorship, seed capital to expertise for optimal utilization of creativity and the ability to market the entrepreneurial idea (Gandhi et al., 2021). After reviewing the relevant literature, it has been inferred that a business incubator in itself is an organization whose main objective is to nurture and support new business firms. To carry out these objectives it requires some inputs like manpower, finance, physical space and ICT infrastructure. Many supporting organisations also needed to contribute to this goal of business incubation.

The researchers find it critical for the policies regarding selection should be positively connected with the achievement of their (business incubators) goals (Hackett and Dilts, 2004; Totterman and Sten, 2005). Therefore, tenant startup firms should disclose correct details regarding their proposed business and company while seeking admission in the business incubator (Pals, 2006). It was also ascertained through literature that business incubators should implement a stringent selection process. With regard to the selection process, it is also

mentioned that those who are ambitious should be given preference during selection for admission in a business incubator (Dvoulety et al., 2018). As we now see, the mission and purpose of a business incubator/incubation centre is to aid in the establishment of new businesses (Churchill and Lewis, 1983; Birley, 1986; Pals, 2006; Al Sharif, 2022).

In this context, the stages of business development become important to mention. There are four stages of business development such as the idea stage, the attempt stage followed by the development stage, and finally the commercialization stage (Bricks, 1986). The study comes to the additional conclusion that the gap linking the idea and the attempt stages is important, and the smaller the gap, the greater the likelihood of establishing a new enterprise. Because of this, incubation aims to minimise the gap between these two stages and inspire independence by providing new business ideas. By offering them a variety of services, such as incubation space, business support services, and professional networking, business incubators are removing the factors that causes to failure for new and small businesses.

A business incubator/incubation centre thus tries to offer proper services and structure to the tenant firms by even sometimes managing their affairs partially and assisting in creation of new undertakings (Smilor, 1987; Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999; Aernoudt, 2004; Chan and Lau, 2005; Gozali, 2020). The main components of business incubators frequently listed and researched in earlier researches are :

- Office space and infrastructure
- Shared services to lessening expenses
- Professional guidance and mentoring
- Financial Support and Marketing assistance
- Networking with other stakeholders

Therefore, it can easily be concluded that business incubators not only support in establishing the new business ventures/startups but also reinforce them in their formative years in the process of their survival when there are more chances of their failure. The business incubator helps new ventures and provides them the goodwill in view of stakeholders as well as its clients (Yannopoulos, 2017; Leitao, 2020). There are various kinds of incubators and the functions/role of these incubators depends upon the type to which they belong.

3. Research Design and Methodology

Management doyen Peter Drucker's famous quote "you can't improve what you don't measure", still stays relevant. In the context of business incubation, it has become imperative to measure the performance of the same as they are either publicly funded or financed by private institutions. On the basis of literature review a conceptual model is developed (Refer Figure 01) for measuring the performance of success factors for business incubators. This study is based on primary data collected from thirty-two business incubation managers and with the aid of SPSS 20.0® and Lisrel 9.00 software, measurement model was assessed.

3.1 Objectives of the Paper

Establishing relationships between existing factors such as Government Policies, affiliation with universities, infrastructural facilities, networking and business incubation success, is the major goal of evaluating the research.

3.2 Research Constructs and Conceptual Relationships

Many researchers in the area of business incubation argued the basis for measuring success of a business incubator is different in every country i.e. it is not a universally accepted criteria (Phan et al., 2005). Some indicators such as formation of networks, support of financial institutions for tenant capitalisation are important measures of performance (Campbell and Allen, 1987). Sustainability and growth of the incubator itself and the tendency of providing services are the mean indicators of incubator performance (Mian, 1997).

As far as India as a developing nation is concerned, it's on growth and development path and at this very stage the role of business incubators becomes pivotal and therefore included in the government's economic development strategy post 2000s. As a result, the current study aims to pinpoint the key success elements influencing incubator outcomes and suggest strategies for improving business incubator performance. This study looks into how connections to universities, infrastructure, and network use might improve the performance of business incubators.

3.2.a. University Linkages

Business incubators linked with academia emphasizes on innovation and growth. Universities are redefining themselves as an entrepreneurial educational hub. Credit goes to their well-developed infrastructure, presence of expert faculty members, access to various databases through libraries, laboratories for R&D,

and alumni connect. Business incubation centres are important for fostering an entrepreneurial culture among students and growing entrepreneurship in a nation, in addition to providing entrepreneurial education and training (Mian, 1997; Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Aerts et al., 2007; Pauwels et al., 2016). Studies emphasize on university linkage and advocates that this construct plays an important role as far as the performance of business incubator is concerned. It is also argued that the type of business incubator depends upon the country in which it is operating and most of the incubators act as research centres under the influence of the university. The incubators in developing nations are either government-funded or foreign-country-funded (Koshi, 2011). The performance and behaviour of business incubator is influenced by the interaction between the university, industry and government in a knowledge-based economy (Etzkowitz, 2009).

3.2.b. Incubation Facilities

The incubation facilities are the set of tangibles provided to the tenant firm like physical space, shared offices, laboratories for R&D for developing prototypes and access to databases for patent search etc. before starting a business. Studies emphasizes on the influence of incubation facilities on enhancing the performance of business incubator. The incubation facilities rages from writing a business plan, supporting product design, developing and testing the prototype, financial assistance and providing workforce and skill-based training to incubatees are the priority support services (Mavuri et al. 2020). The facilities are of immense importance at every incubation phase. In a pre-incubation phase when the business incubators are facilitating new business plans, knowledge intensive business techniques are being provided. In the incubation phase financial services and business development services are being provided and in post incubation stage a business incubator extends its support to the firms successfully graduated from the business incubator (Fernandez et al., 2015).

3.2.c. Networking

Another important construct behind success of any business incubator is a network with the different agencies for knowledge sharing, obtaining finance and smooth operations, stems from the network theory (Nohria and Eccles, 1992). This theory advocates the main feature of business incubator is to channelize the knowledge for the development of its clients and find out ways to commercialize the innovations. The use of networks for the enhancement of the performance of business incubator/incubation centre is well mentioned in several

studies and considered that networking can be used as a major strategy to benefit both incubator and incubatee (Akcomak, 2009). Like other incubator facilities, networking facilities also helps business incubator/incubation centre in different stages of the incubation process and exploitation of networks acts as a critical success factor for any business incubator (McCann, Reuer and Lahiri, 2016). Networking can be made efficient both internally as well as externally, the robustness of internal networks enhances the competitiveness of a business incubator (Hughes, Ireland and Morgan, 2007; Leitão, 2022) on the other hand the robustness of external factors helps the entrepreneurs in getting and procuring many important resources needed to survive in the market (Eveleens, van Rijnsoever and Niesten, 2017).

3.2.d. Business Incubator Performance

Till date there is no consensus on the definition and the way to measure business incubator performance but many researchers show interest in this area. Few studies tried to define and assess performance of business incubators (Ayatse, Kwahar, and Iyortsuun, 2017; Eveleens, vanRijnsoever and Niesten, 2017; Gozali, 2020; Pattanasak, 2022). We have to consider some definitions of performance of business incubator in order to develop a conceptual model as the performance is generally referred as the goal attainment activity in comparison to the expected outcome (Mosselman and Prince, 2004). It is worth mentioning that the goal of a business incubator should be centred on the clients' successful graduation in order to accommodate new admissions.

The number of successful graduates is therefore regarded as a sign of a constructive incubation process. Survival rate and graduation rate become significant when evaluating the effectiveness of a business incubator. In a similar vein, business incubators are renowned for producing jobs (Brooks, 1986; Al-Mubarak and Busler, 2010). Consequently, an incubator should foster an inventive culture and provide support for technology transfer (Mian, 1997; Phillips, 2002). Studies also argued that business incubators are crucial in the development of industry clusters and economic growth (Hansen et al. 2000; Fukugawa, 2013). The items pertaining to all these sub-constructs can be added to the scale while measuring the performance of a business incubator.

3.3 Conceptual Model of Research

A Conceptual model should have both independent and dependent variables (Anderson & Gerbing, 1991). The model specification of the study may be given as :

$$\text{BIP} = f \{ \text{UL}, \text{NG}, \text{IF} \}$$

BIP = Business Incubator Performance (Endogenous/Dependent variable).

UL = University linkage (Exogenous/Independent variable).

IF = Incubator Facilities (Exogenous/Independent variable).

NG = Networking (Exogenous/Independent variable).

Figure-1 : Conceptual Model for Study Constructs

3.4 Respondents Profile

The data was collected from a sample of 32 respondents, 56.2 percent of the sample of 32 people were women, 75.4 percent were single, and 20.8% of people were married, and the average age was 30. Regarding education levels, 14.1 percent finished higher education, while the highest level of education held by 10% of those was a postgraduate degree. We created the first goal of the article to validate the components utilised by factorial confirmatory analysis once we knew the profile of the respondents.

4. Analysis

Assessment of Unidimensionality, Reliability and Validity

The magnitude of the factorial load must also be observed in CFA, and variables with low loadings should be eliminated from the model. Cronbach’s alpha (Cronbach, 1951) was used to assess the construct’s dependability, with values greater than 0.7 being acceptable. By analysing standardised residuals, it is possible to confirm the construct’s unidimensionality. The results for CFA are shown in Figure-2.

Figure-2 : CFA for all Study Scales

Convergent validity was also established through independent t test. The values for all the scales were above recommended 1.96. The results are shown in Figure-3.

Figure-3 : t Values to Establish Convergent Validity

Table-1 : Test Results of Validity & Reliability

Construct	Cronbach Alpha	Construct Reliability	Variance Extracted
UL	.77	.79	.46
NG	.84	.96	.80
IF	.88	.89	.67
BIP	.85	.85	.55

Source : Computation by the author.

5. Conclusion

This study is useful for further investigation on the condition of incubators right now and what initiatives are required for the advancement of business incubators in the future. The research instrument is established from the comprehensive literature review and measures are identified. Only a conceptual model is developed in this study from data which is obtained from 32 incubation managers. It can be empirically tested in future research by conducting a quantitative survey of a subset of Indian BIs.

Through this data the research scale was refined and testing required for the assessment of the measurement model was performed. Initially, CFA was performed and all the scales were found unidimensional. Further, tests of validity and reliability were also performed, where the scale was found valid and reliable. The existing research serves as a foundation and identifies relationships that could be enhanced and reinforced by a cross-sectional/longitudinal or even a case-based analysis of business incubators' best practices. Therefore, we propose that this scale can be used for further research and the findings obtained can be generalized.

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